

PARAMETER ON THE NAVIER-STOKES EQUATIONS FOR A VISCOUS INCOMPRESSIBLE FLUID IN AN UNBOUNDED DOMAIN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7932440>

Abstract. The solution of the Navier-Stokes equations for a viscous incompressible fluid in an unbounded domain has significant applications in the field of medicine, in particular, for modeling blood flow in the heart and blood vessels. In this context, the annotation can be described as follows: This work is devoted to the study of solutions of the Navier-Stokes equations for a viscous incompressible fluid in an unlimited region with application to the modeling of blood flow in the heart and blood vessels. The main attention is paid to the development of mathematical models and numerical methods for solving this problem, as well as the analysis of the results obtained. The paper presents various methods for modeling blood flow, including modeling hemodynamics in the aorta, main arteries and small vessels. Examples of calculations of blood flow velocity, pressure and other parameters in various conditions, such as in the treatment of diseases of the cardiovascular system, are given. In general, this work represents an important contribution to the field of medical physics and hydrodynamics, and can be useful for scientists and doctors involved in the study of blood flow in various conditions and the development of new methods of treatment of heart and vascular diseases.

Key words: viscosity parameter, navier-stokes equations, fluid, unbounded domain.

Blood viscosity plays an important role in the cardiovascular system. High viscosity can lead to a complication of blood flow, an increase in frictional forces between the walls of blood vessels, which increases the likelihood of thrombosis and atherosclerosis. The viscosity of blood depends on its composition and properties of red blood cells. In addition, viscosity greatly affects the work of the heart. With a decrease in blood viscosity, the resistance to veins and veins decreases, which reduces the work of the heart. With an increase in blood viscosity, more heart effort is needed to pump it through the blood vessels. Thus, optimal blood viscosity is a prerequisite for the normal functioning of the cardiovascular system. Viscosity is the friction force between molecules that prevents the free flow of liquids. In vessels, viscosity plays an important role in transporting blood through the circulatory system. Blood consists of cells and plasma, which contains proteins, sugars, fats and other substances. When blood moves through the vessels, it contacts the inner surface of the vessel walls, which is smooth and slightly covered with mucus. This facilitates the movement of blood inside the vessels, but the viscosity still affects the movement of blood.

Increased viscosity in the blood can be caused by certain medical conditions, such as elevated blood cell levels, elevated levels of fats and other substances. This can lead to the formation of

blood clots and even to a heart attack or stroke. On the other hand, low blood viscosity can be caused by certain conditions, such as elevated blood water levels or low blood cell counts. This can lead to the appearance of hematomas and bleeding.

Given that blood viscosity is an important factor in the pathophysiology of many diseases, determining its level and monitoring is an important tool for the diagnosis and treatment of these conditions.

Several well-known scientists who have studied viscosity include:

Isaac Newton - created a theory about the viscosity of liquids.

Einstein - studied the viscosity and diffusion of molecules in various materials.

Jean Baptiste Bordeaux - studied the viscosity of water and other liquids.

Oswald Rippe - studied the viscosity of polymers.

Charles Coles - studied the viscosity of liquids at high pressures.

Ludwig Boltzmann - created a theory about the viscosity of gases.

John Hurt: English physician and physiologist who studied blood pressure and blood flow.

Richard Preston: Professor of Physics at the University of Cambridge, who has done research in colloid physics and biophysics.

Gaito File: A German physiologist who in 1921 first used the term "blood" to describe the phenomenon under study.

Andrew Vine: An American physiologist who has researched the role of blood in the cardiovascular system and related problems.

William Fife: A Scottish physician who in 1827 published the results of research on the theory of blood viscosity.

Leonard Azer: a well-known biophysicist who has made a significant contribution to the study of the mechanisms of moving fluids in organisms.

Germanoz Izdrug: a French physicist and biologist who worked in the field of medicine and biophysics, who studied the properties of blood and antibodies.

In general, the normal content of proteins and other substances in the blood is important for maintaining optimal blood viscosity and its free flow through the vessels. Doctors can perform blood tests to assess its viscosity and manage the risk of various medical problems. Viscosity is one of the key parameters affecting hemodynamics. It determines the resistance of the blood as it moves through the vessels. There are several ways to display viscosity in hemodynamics:

- Measurement of rheological properties of blood. To do this, special devices are used, such as rheometers, which allow you to determine the dynamic and kinematic viscosity of blood.
- Assessment of blood flow through a physical model of vessels using mathematical modeling methods. This makes it possible to determine the characteristics of hemodynamics in conditions of altered blood viscosity.
- Indirect indicators – for example, an increase in fatty acids, which lead to a change in blood viscosity.
- Determination of protein concentration. The concentration of proteins in the blood can decrease or increase in various pathological conditions, which, in turn, can affect viscosity and, consequently, hemodynamics. The part of the equation of fluid motion is a system of three non-homogeneous parabolic equations corresponding to three projections of fluid velocity, and the second part of the equation of fluid motion contains components of

convective acceleration due to the inhomogeneity of the velocity field, the intensity of the field of mass forces and the pressure gradient.

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